

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	Gabi Project
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.7493 Max: 63.1344	1340 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropoc	

In cross-section? Yes No
 In elevation drawing? Yes No
 Photos: Yes No #: 1547-1548
 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: soil abutting 1320
 Covered by: SU: (M)
 Fills: SU:
 Filled by: SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery f <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles f <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae f <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mortar f <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Glass r	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nails r <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster m <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) burnt pipe-not iron hook/latch + slag	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) f <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone f <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	clay 5% silt 85% sand 10% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction: <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Soft Color: <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: _____ Is bound to (only for masonry): _____
 Is abuted by: 1320, 1058 on western edge, 1327 Abuts: _____
 Is covered by: (M) Covers: 1384, 1401
 Is cut by: _____ Cuts: _____
 Is filled by: _____ Fills: _____

OBSERVATIONS: Big patch of tufo inclusions (robber) in center-western part of 1340 on wall 1162; iron hook and lots of charcoal + burnt bone found on edges of also found a burnt pipe-not in south-western corner. Tufo "patch".

DESCRIPTION: Position within sector: Lower southwestern corner near 2011 excavation limit
 Shape: roughly rectangular w/ northern projection along wall 1162 and eastern curve around tufo floor

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): slopes downward toward south + excavation limit (2011)
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): tufo inclusion patch w/ iron hook + slag, lots of charcoal + some burnt bone on eastern side of tufo patch
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): decreases in thickness in south-western corner of SU
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Soil abutting B20 contained clusters of various types including a tub "rubble pile-esque patch" in the western-central area, around which the other deposits were scattered; iron hoops, slag, other metal; burnt bones, a pine-nut and charcoal. Additionally there were high frequencies of tile + pottery shards; the whole SU was bounded by wall SU 1162 and another or several other walls as well as partially covered the fragmentary tufo floor to the east which appears to go over one of the walls suggesting multiple occupation layers. This accumulation layer seems to be a mix of debris from various activities.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by SJK, mm

on 6/30/11

Revised by CFH

on 13/7/11

PDFd by AMS

on 21/7/11

Entered by

on